

regions reported by Sacconi *et al* were obtained. Hence, these two compounds have a pseudo-tetrahedral configuration in conformity with the earlier observations⁸.

The X-ray powder photograph of the two complexes $[L]_2$, $[CuCl_4(\nu\text{-pic})_2]$ and $[L]_2[CuCl_4(An)_2]$ have been studied. The grazing angle (θ) and the lattice spacing value (d) have been calculated. This study indicates that the two complexes belong to the cubic system having the unit cell dimensions of 3.079 Å and 3.200 Å respectively.

Acknowledgement

The author (R. P. M.) is obliged to both Dr. Sunil K. Sarangi, Assistant Professor, Cryogenic Engineering Centre, IIT, Kharagpur and Dr. S. Torasia, Reader, Department of Physics, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack for the help in recording the X-ray powder photographs.

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Studies of Cation Exchange Behaviour of Magnesium Trisilicate

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Manuscript received 13 September 1978, revised 17 November 1979, accepted 31 March 1980

MAGNESIUM trisilicate (MTS) has been used for chromatographic separation of organic compounds by several workers¹⁻⁵. No attempt has, however, been made to study the sorption behaviour of inorganic ions using MTS. The present study reports the sorption behaviour of MTS, under static conditions, using some metal complexes of identical formal charge but differing in size and shape such as ammine complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II).

Experimental

Magnesium trisilicate (MTS): It was obtained from E. Merck and treated with 2N HCl for 24 hrs to remove any soluble impurity. The free HCl was removed by washing with water. Finally, it was dried at 100° for 14 hrs and stored in a desiccator.

The ammine complexes were prepared by dissolving appropriate quantities of individual metal sulphate in aqueous ammonia containing ammonium sulphate (buffer). All experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 3^\circ$.

Determination of the amounts of the metal complexes sorbed: 0.5 gm of MTS was mixed with 25 ml of a sample of metal complex solution of specific composition and pH value. After shaking for three hrs (sufficient to reach equilibrium), the solid was separated by centrifuge. 5 ml of portions of aliquot were analysed for the metal ions complexometrically⁶. The difference in the metal concentration before and after sorption corresponded to the amount of the metal complex retained on MTS. The distribution coefficient (Kd) and selectivity quotients were determined using the formulae reported earlier^{7,8}.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in Tables 1 and 2 bring out the following interesting points:

1. The q_0 values increase with increasing concentration of metal solutions up to a certain concentration (0.05M) and then decrease (Table 1). The Kd values decrease with increase of concentration.
2. Zn(II) has maximum sorption of all the metal complexes studied (Table 1).
3. In general, selectivity quotients are adversely affected by an increase in the concentration of the exchanging ion (Table 2).

TABLE 1—CONCENTRATION DEPENDENCE OF SORPTION OF METAL COMPLEXES OF MTS

Initial conc. of the external soln. (molar)	Amount of the exchanging ion per samp. (meq.)	Conc. of the buffer soln. (molar)	Amount Sorbed (q ₀ in meq.)				Kd × 10 ³							
			Amount of the MTS=0.5 gm pH=8.5 Volume of the external solution=25 ml				Zn(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)	Zn(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)
			Zn(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)	Zn(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)				
0.01	0.5	0.10	0.47	0.46	0.15	0.39	82.83	5.75	0.21	0.69				
0.02	1.0	0.20	0.68	0.51	0.18	0.31	1.06	0.52	0.11	0.22				
0.05	5.5	0.50	0.72	0.53	0.23	0.33	0.20	0.13	0.05	0.08				
0.08	4.0	0.80	0.70	0.42	0.21	0.31	0.10	0.06	0.03	0.04				
0.10	5.0	1.00	0.62	0.33	0.17	0.28	0.07	0.03	0.02	0.03				

TABLE 2—CONCENTRATION DEPENDENCE OF THE SELECTIVITY QUOTIENT

Amount of the MTS=0.5 gm
Volume of the external solution=25 ml
pH=8.5
Metal : Buffer=1 : 10

System	Concentration of each species (molar)	q ₀ (meq)		Selectivity quotient
		Cu(II)	Zn(II)	
Cu(II)-Zn(II)	0.01	0.22	0.27	K _{Zn} ^{Cu} 0.67
	0.05	0.14	0.61	0.18
	0.08	0.13	0.60	0.19
	0.10	0.13	0.50	0.24
Cu(II)-Cd(II)		Cu(II)	Cd(II)	K _{Cd} ^{Cu}
	0.01	0.41	0.21	6.29
	0.05	0.46	0.28	1.78
	0.08	0.39	0.25	1.62
Cu(II)-Ni(II)		Cu(II)	Ni(II)	K _{Ni} ^{Cu}
	0.01	0.40	0.12	12.66
	0.05	0.48	0.16	3.47
	0.08	0.36	0.13	2.73
	0.10	0.36	0.11	3.44

Cd(II) < Cu(II) < Ni(II). The corresponding values of ionic potential (charge/radius) which is known to be directly related to the sorption capacity would be in reverse order. This is in agreement with the observed order of sorption capacity.

A closer look on selectivity quotients (Table 2) would show that Zn(II) is the most preferred ion followed by Cu(II), Cd(II) and Ni(II). The decrease of selectivity quotients with increasing concentrations show that activity of the competing ions in the solid phase assumes more dominant role. This view is supported by the finding of Samuelson¹⁴ and other workers^{15,16} while investigating the selectivity effects in various ion exchange resins. The sudden increase of selectivity quotients at 0.1M can be understood from the fact that the decrease in q₀ in Cu(II) complex at this concentration is relatively less in comparison to other metal complexes.

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The observed decrease in the equilibrium sorption beyond the external concentration 0.05M is presumably due to the possible lowering of ionic activity at higher concentration⁹. The exchanging ions used in the present study have identical formal charges, so it may not be unreasonable to make some estimation of the ionic size of the complexes, on the basis of their known symmetry¹⁰ and crystallographic covalent radii^{11,12}, of central metal atoms [tetrahedral, Zn(II)-1.31 Å and Cd(II)-1.48 Å ; Cu(II) with a staggered octahedral structure in Cu{(NH₃)₄.2H₂O}SO₄, 4Cu-N=2.05 Å, Cu-Cu-OH₂=2.59 Å, Cu-OH₂=3.37 Å] and octahedral Ni(II)-1.39 Å. Under the experimental conditions, metal complex ions exist^{11,12} as :

In the light of above facts, the order of the ionic radii of the complexes would be Zn(II) <

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A Selective and Sensitive Method for Detection of Nitro Compounds

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NITROCOMPOUNDS are of wide interest in industry where many of them find use as solvents and intermediates in the preparation of certain pharmaceuticals, insecticides, dyes, textile and explosive chemicals. This group of compounds, with few exceptions, has toxicological effects and causes methemoglobinemia in warm blooded animals and man⁷. For these reasons, the method for their detection and estimation in micro quantity carries special importance.

Some methods have been reported in the literature for the micro determination of nitro compounds¹⁻⁵ but very few methods are known for their detection in trace quantity⁶, none of which is applicable to both aliphatic and aromatic series of nitro compounds. The present method reported here is rapid and simple and is applicable for the detection of both the classes of nitro compounds.

The method is based on the fact that nitro compounds are reduced by zinc and ammonium chloride in neutral solution to the corresponding hydroxylamines which with acid chloride forms N-substituted hydroxamic acids. These hydroxamic acids give brilliant purple or blue-violet chloroform extractable complexes⁸ with V(V) in 3-8M hydrochloric acid medium. These coloured complexes can also be extracted in other water immiscible solvents such as benzene, ether, *o*-dichlorobenzene etc.

Experimental

Pure BDH and E. Merck nitro compounds were used. A stock solution of the nitro compounds was prepared by dissolving 5-100 mg of the compound

in alcohol in a 100 ml measuring flask. An aliquot of the stock solution was diluted to the desired concentration.

Procedure :

In a micro centrifuge tube mix 2 drops (approx. 0.1 ml) of sample solution (alcoholic) with 2-4 drops of water. To this add a pinch of ammonium chloride (2-3 mg) and zinc dust (3-4 mg). Shake well and heat for 2-4 minutes on a water bath at 70-80°, centrifuge and decant the supernatant liquid into a micro test tube. Wash the residue in the centrifuge tube with 0.5 ml ether and decant into the same micro test tube and shake. To this add one drop of benzoyl chloride and shake gently for some time. Add one drop of chloroform, 4 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and one drop of saturated solution of ammonium metavanadate. Shake the mixture vigorously for 2-3 min and allow the phases to separate. If nitro compound is present, the chloroform layer turns purple or blue violet. The colour development in the chloroform layer is more readily perceived when a white porcelain background is used.

This method was found suitable for the detection of a large number of nitro compounds. Identification limits of some of the nitro compounds were determined which are given in Table 1.

Phenols, salicylic acid and hydroxylamines interfere in the detection.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour of chloroform extract	Identification* limits, mg
Nitrobenzene	Violet	0.05
<i>o</i> -, <i>m</i> - and <i>p</i> -nitrotoluene	,,	0.05
<i>p</i> -chloronitrobenzene	,,	0.042
2 : 5 dichloronitrobenzene	,,	0.042
2-nitronaphthalene	Blue violet	0.045
Nitro methane	Purple	0.1
Nitro ethane	,,	0.1

* These quantities were present in 0.1 ml of sample solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. S. G. Tandon, Professor and Head of Chemistry Department, Ravishankar University, Raipur (M.P.) for providing necessary facilities. B. R. Sahu is also grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship.

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